

ISic0431

I.Sicily inscription 0431

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 236

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Fulvius · Nic[o]
2. vixit · annis · L ·
3. Fulvius · Ianuarius
4. vixit · annum · I ·
5. menses · III

Apparatus

Text from CIL

Translation (en)

Fulvius Nico, he lived fifty years. Fulvius Januarius, he lived one year and three months.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491659

EDCS 21900493

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7151 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650768>)

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